

Study Protocol MoCAVaR Neck

Movement Control Assessment in patients with chronic neck pain: Validity and Reliability

1 BACKGROUND AND PROJECT RATIONALE

Chronic neck pain is a leading cause of disability (Vos et al., 2015) and represents significant personal, economic and health care burdens (Safiri et al., 2020). The one-year prevalence of neck pain among adults ranges from 16.7% to 75.1% (mean 37.2%) (Fejer et al., 2006). Between 50% to 85% of patients with an episode of neck pain at a certain moment will report recurrent neck pain within the next five years (Carroll et al., 2008), highlighting the often chronic-episodic nature of neck pain (Hogg-Johnson et al., 2008). Managing patients with chronic neck pain remains a significant challenge in physiotherapy because neck pain is a multifaceted problem (Côté et al., 2003) and patients with neck pain form a very heterogenic group (Childs et al., 2004).

In clinical practice, movement control measures are used to assess active neck movements and identify difficulties in controlling these neck movements in patients with chronic neck pain. The term movement control is not always described uniformly in the literature. For our research, inspired by Luomajoki et al. (2008) and Patroncini et al. (2014) we define movement control as the ability to perform active movements by maintaining a harmonic alignment of the segments (i.e., no shift) with an appropriate muscle response. If movement control measures yield negative results, no impairment is attributed to movement control. Conversely, positive outcomes on movement control measures indicate impaired movement control, which might contribute to the severity and/or recurrence of neck pain. In the context of low back pain, movement control measures have shown to produce reliable and valid results (Adelt et al., 2021; Luomajoki et al., 2008, 2010). Current guidelines for the management of low back pain recommend to incorporate movement control exercises in the management of patients with chronic low back and leg pain (recommendation level B) as well as in patients with chronic low back pain with movement control impairment (recommendation level A) (George et al., 2021). However, in contrast to low back pain, the available research on movement control in patients with neck pain remains limited.

A number of measures assessing movement control of the neck have been studied for their reliability (Patroncini et al., 2014; Segarra et al., 2015). In both studies, reliability was investigated in a mixed population including subjects with neck pain and subjects without neck pain and reliability was not reported for the group with neck pain separately. However, reliability values for a measure are only useful if the reliability has been studied in the population in which the measure is used in clinical practice. In addition, both studies looked at the measures for movement control based on video recordings, which means that the studies investigated how reliable the physiotherapists were in rating the measurement, but other aspects as the instruction and execution of the measurement were not investigated.

Ernst et al. (2022) investigated inter-rater reliability, discriminatory and predictive validity of movement control measures of the neck. While they focused in their study on office workers with headache and/or neck pain, we are interested in patients with chronic neck pain. Furthermore, the measures in our study are not the same as the measures investigated by Ernst et al. They distinguished between movement control measures for the upper and the lower cervical spine, while only two out of the 10 measures in our selection require movement

only in the upper or middle/lower cervical spine and are not the same measures as in the study by Ernst et al. For the other eight measures in our study, a movement of the cervical spine is required without differentiating upper or lower cervical spine. To our knowledge, our study is the first to examine construct validity of movement control measures of the neck.

Although movement control measures for the neck are widely used in clinical practice, no consensus is available on which of these measures are clinically useful in patients with chronic neck pain. To address this gap, we conducted a Delphi study aiming to reach consensus among international experts (researchers and clinicians) in the field of movement control and neck pain regarding the clinical usefulness of specific measures for the assessment of movement control in patients with chronic neck pain (paper in preparation). We systematically collected all available measures for the assessment of movement control for the cervical spine in a systematic review (Elsig et al., 2023). Consequently, participants of the Delphi study were asked to indicate whether each measure was clinically useful or not. Ultimately, 10 of the 38 measures that were presented in the Delphi study were deemed clinically useful by 75% or more of the experts. In our upcoming project, we will investigate the measurement properties of the 10 remaining measures.

The 10 measures will be assessed on reliability and involved in a validity investigation: three out of them as index measures and another selection as comparator validity. Reliability refers to the extent to which a test is free from measurement error (Mokkink et al., 2010), while validity indicates the degree to which the test accurately measures the intended construct, in other words: “measuring what you want to measure” (Mokkink et al., 2010). With the outcomes of this research, we ultimately aim to offer guidance to physiotherapists in clinical practice on the use of movement control measures in patients with chronic neck pain. To be able to do this, we need to know reliability and validity of a number of measures that are used in clinical physiotherapy practice. We focus in this study on the measurement properties inter-rater reliability, discriminative validity and construct validity.

Inter-rater reliability is important, because we want to investigate, how reliable the selected measures are if they are applied by different physiotherapists working with this type of patients. The physiotherapists in our study represent a random sample of all physiotherapists, and we are interested in agreement regarding the consistency of the decision of each physiotherapist for an individual patient if the outcome is positive or negative.

Furthermore, we will investigate discriminative validity of the movement control measures, i.e., in our study the ability of the measures to differentiate between participants with and without chronic neck pain. In our study, participants will answer a standardised question if they are suffering from chronic neck pain or not. The answer to this question will serve as gold standard. We present the a priori defined criterion for accepting discriminative validity of the measures.

Lastly, we will explore construct validity, which in the context of this project is defined as the degree to which the obtained scores of a measurement instrument are consistent with the formulated hypotheses based on relationships with scores of other measures (De Vet et al., 2011). We have selected three index measures for which specific hypotheses are presented. These hypotheses will outline expectations regarding the direction and strength of correlations with other measures based on the comparison of their underlying theoretical constructs. Criteria for the acceptance of construct validity based on the proportion of confirmed hypotheses out the whole number of hypotheses are determined a priori.

Therefore, the aims of the study are a) to investigate inter-rater reliability and discriminative validity of 10 movement control measures, and b) to investigate construct validity of three selected index measures with their specific comparators, chosen out of the same 10 movement control measures.

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND DESIGN

2.1 Hypothesis and primary objective

The study has two primary objectives: first, to obtain data on inter-rater reliability and second to obtain data on validity of 10 movement control measures. In terms of validity, we will examine discriminative validity of the 10 movement control measures and construct validity of three index measures with their specific comparators chosen out of the same 10 movement control measures in patients with chronic neck pain.

The hypotheses to measure construct validity are as follows:

1. The active cervical flexion and extension test (through entire range) will show a positive correlation of 0.7–0.9 with the active cervical rotation test (through entire range). The task of returning to neutral position after an active movement is asked in both measures and therefore the underlying concept is comparable, and we expect a high correlation.
2. The active cervical flexion and extension test (through entire range) will show a positive correlation of 0.2–0.4 with the bilateral arm flexion with weights test (90°). In the first measure, the task is to move the cervical spine actively, whether in the second test, the cervical spine must remain stable while the shoulder joints (adjacent joints) do an active movement. We consider this to be different concepts and therefore expect a low correlation between the two measures.
3. The active cervical rotation test (through entire range) will show a positive correlation of 0.6–0.8 with the active cervical lateral flexion test (through entire range). Patients who find it difficult to perform a rotation without another component of movement will often perform a lateral flexion at the same time as the rotation. And patients that have difficulty to perform a pure movement of lateral flexion, often do a simultaneous rotation movement. Therefore, we think that if one of the movements is difficult for a patient, the other movement is also difficult.
4. The active cervical rotation test (through entire range) will show a positive correlation of 0.3–0.5 with the active cervical extension in four-point kneeling. The first measure demand active movement through the entire range of motion with the whole cervical spine participating in the movement. The movement axis is vertical, and the focus of the task is to keep the nose horizontal, i.e. to avoid a tilt of the movement axis. In the second measure, the axis of movement is horizontal, and the focus of the task is to move the lower/middle cervical spine and avoid the contribution of the upper cervical spine to the movement. We think that these are different tasks and expect a low correlation between these two measures.
5. The bilateral arm flexion test (180°) will show a positive correlation of 0.6–0.8 with the unilateral arm flexion test (180°). In both measures, the patient must reactively stabilise the cervical spine during movements of adjacent joints, once moving both arms and once moving only one arm. We think that the task of reactive stabilization of the cervical spine is more challenging in the bilateral arm movement than in the unilateral movement, but as both measures assess the same concept of reactive stabilisation of the cervical spine, we expect a high correlation.
6. The bilateral arm flexion test (180°) will show a positive correlation of 0.2–0.4 with the upper cervical extension test (in four-point kneeling). We think that these two measures assess two different aspects of movement control: reactive stabilisation of the cervical spine during an active movement of big range in adjacent joints in the first test versus an active movement of the cervical spine itself with very little range of movement in the second test. Therefore, we expect a small correlation between these two measures.

To confirm construct validity of the 10 movement control measures, our a priori defined criteria are that a) four out of the six hypotheses should be confirmed and b) in all three index measures at least one of the hypotheses should be confirmed.

2.2 Primary and secondary endpoints

For inter-rater reliability the primary endpoint is unweighted Cohen's Kappa (kappa value and 95% CI). The data will be interpreted based on the classification of Landis and Koch (1977).

For discriminative validity, the primary endpoint is sensitivity and specificity. We accept a lower boundary of 0.7 for sensitivity and specificity for the confirmation of discriminative validity.

For construct validity, the primary endpoint is the correlation of the measures (Pearson correlation).

2.3 Project design

A cross-sectional design investigating inter-rater reliability, discriminative validity and construct validity will be conducted. This is a monocentric study conducted at different sites of the same institution (HES-SO Valais-Wallis).

3 PROJECT POPULATION AND STUDY PROCEDURES

3.1 Project population, inclusion and exclusion criteria

3.1.1 Study participants

The study participants will consist of participants with chronic neck pain and participants without neck pain. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the participation in the study are described in table 1. Following the recommendations from the COSMIN group, we plan to collect complete sets from 50 participants with chronic neck pain and 50 participants without neck pain (De Vet et al., 2011). We anticipate a potential drop-out rate of 10% (e.g. participants unable to complete the measures due to pain or other reasons) and therefore plan to recruit 56 participants in each group. The recruitment will be gender neutral. We aim to have a population of participants with chronic neck pain that is as close as possible to the patients with chronic neck pain that present in physiotherapy practices for treatment.

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for study participants

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Participants with chronic neck pain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chronic or recurrent neck pain of more than 3 months duration, whereby neck pain is defined as pain perceived in the anatomical region of the neck with or without radiation to the head, trunk, and upper limbs. The neck region is defined from the superior nuchal line to the spine of the scapula and the side region down to the superior border of the clavicle and the suprasternal notch (Misailidou et al., 2010) Age between 18 and 70 years Able to understand written and verbal instructions in French or German 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any medical disorder where active neck movements would be contraindicated or where a more severe pathology is suspected (red flags) Specific neck pain, like herniated disk or spinal fracture Acute neck pain that prevents free active neck movement
Participants without neck pain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No current neck pain No history of chronic neck pain, i.e. neck pain episode of more than 3 months duration No surgery in the neck region in the past Age between 18 and 70 years Able to understand written and verbal instructions in French or German 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Note: Whiplash-associated disorder (WAD) as well as headache if it is in combination with neck pain are not exclusion criteria

3.1.2 Physiotherapists

The physiotherapists carrying out the measurements must meet the inclusion criteria listed in table 2. We have deliberately not defined selection criteria relating to specific continuing education, as the physiotherapists carrying out the measurements should be representative of the general population of physiotherapists.

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for physiotherapists

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Physiotherapist working in clinical practice, clinic or hospital• Treat patients with chronic neck pain• Very good knowledge of German or French	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Physiotherapists who do not work clinically with patients

3.2 Recruitment, screening and informed consent procedure

3.2.1 Study participants

Participants will be recruited through advertisements in physiotherapy practices, at the Leukerbad Clinic (recruitment through referring physiotherapists) and among students and employees at the University of Applied Sciences Valais-Wallis (HES-SO Valais-Wallis). Only students who are not enrolled in the bachelor's degree programme in physiotherapy and who have no connection with the project leader or the physiotherapists carrying out the measurements will be recruited. We will also post a flyer in physiotherapy practices and on LinkedIn to recruit participants. Interested persons with and without neck pain will receive the study information sheet containing information about the study as well as the informed consent form. If they have any questions about the study, they can use the contact address in the study information. They have at least 24 hours to decide whether or not to take part in the study.

Persons with chronic neck pain and persons without neck pain who agree to participate in the study must give their written informed consent. The project leader (SE), who is not involved in the testing of the participants, will contact the participants. She will subsequently include or exclude participants on the basis of pre-defined criteria (see table 1) and, if the inclusion criteria are met, arrange a measurement appointment with the participants. Participants in the study will be reimbursed for travel expenses (car park, public transport).

3.2.2 Physiotherapists

As the measurements will take place at the HES-SO Valais-Wallis, we will use the HES-SO Valais-Wallis physiotherapy department's network to recruit the physiotherapists. This network comprises around 80 physiotherapists who work in clinical settings such as physiotherapy practices, hospitals and clinics. In line with the snowball principle, we also have access to other physiotherapists through these physiotherapists and their respective work teams. Physiotherapists who are interested in taking part in the study will receive an information sheet describing the study and detailing what will be expected of them. They will be able to contact the project leader if they have any questions. Physiotherapists must commit to a minimum of one measurement day but can commit to more according to their availability. We will need physiotherapists to cover 10-12 measurement days with two physiotherapists per day. We need a minimum of two and a maximum of 24 physiotherapist, depending on how many measurement days the individual physiotherapists are willing to participate in. Physiotherapists can indicate if they can do the measurements in French, in German or in both languages. They will be allocated to the test days according to their availability, taking the language into account. Furthermore, physiotherapists will be allocated to test locations that do not correspond to their place of work. The physiotherapists will have to provide written informed consent before

participating in their first measurement day. They will be paid for the hours that they work on the project.

3.3 Study procedures

The recruitment of participants and the measurement sessions will start in August 2025 and will last until the end of March 2026. The project leader (SE) will be present at all measurement sessions to ensure randomized allocation of participants to the physiotherapists and the correct running of the measurement sessions.

Prior to the measurement sequence and in the absence of the physiotherapist, the project leader will ask the standardised question that will serve as gold standard. (Do you have neck pain for more than 3 months? By neck pain for more than 3 months, we mean that you have constant or recurring episodes of neck pain for more than 3 months. Yes/No). Based on this question, the participants will be assigned to the corresponding study group (participants with chronic neck pain or participants without neck pain). Then, the project leader (SE) will ask the participants to rate their current neck pain intensity on a numeric rating scale (NRS). This will be done before each measurement sequence to observe whether participants had different pain levels between the first and the second measurement sequence. The project leader will then randomly assign the participants to physiotherapist 1 or physiotherapist 2. The two physiotherapists will independently assess the 10 movement control measures and will be blinded to the condition of the participant (chronic neck pain or no neck pain) and to each other's assessments. Participants will be instructed not to disclose their condition.

The 10 movement control measures encompass assessments for each movement direction (flexion, extension, rotation, and lateral flexion) in different measurement positions (sitting, standing, four-point kneeling), measures in which the cervical spine is moved and measures in which an adjacent joint is moved, while maintaining stability of the cervical spine without movement (table 3).

Table 3.: Description of the 10 movement control measures

Active cervical flexion	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is sitting with the neck and head in an upright position. The patient then flexes the cervical spine and brings the chin as close as possible to the sternum and returns to the upright position.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imprecise movement • Altered distribution of flexion in the cervical spine
Active cervical extension	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is asked to look up at the ceiling and follow the ceiling back with the eyes as far as possible (mouth open).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The patient is unwilling to allow the centre of gravity of the head to move posteriorly behind the frontal plane of the shoulders • The head reaches a point of extension and then appears to fall or translate backwards (loss of control)
Active cervical flexion and extension (through entire range)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient flexes the cervical spine so that the chin moves towards the sternum. The patient then extends the cervical spine into extension as far as possible (mouth open) and finally returns to the upright position.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ventral head translation or protraction instead of rotation around an axis in the ear during flexion • Deficient upper cervical spine flexion • Non-harmonic movement
Active cervical extension in four-point kneeling	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient imagines that he or she has a book between the hands. The physiotherapist instructs the patient to look down and bend the head and neck together as far as the patient can, and then to bring the head back up as far as the patient can (lower and middle cervical spine), but to keep the eyes on the book throughout the movement.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to dissociate mid-lower from upper cervical extension • Inability to achieve 20° of cervical extension while keeping the cranio-cervical region in neutral. • Poor coordination strategy with excessive use of superficial cervical muscles, indicated by cranio-cervical extension, and excessive use of the semispinalis capitis muscles, indicated by marked prominence at the back of the neck
Active cervical rotation (through entire range)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is asked to turn the head to the right and back to the middle position, then to the left and back to the middle position. Finally, the patient is asked to turn the head once through the whole range from right to left without stopping in the middle position and to return to the starting position.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nose not remaining horizontal • Evasive head movements in protraction, extension, flexion or lateral flexion • Non-rhythmic movements, staccato

Active cervical lateral flexion (through entire range)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is asked to tilt the head to the right and back to the middle position, then to the left and back to the middle position, and finally to move once from the right to the left without stopping in the middle position.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cervical spine rotation • Shoulder elevation • Non-rhythmic movement, staccato • Protraction of the head or chin
Unilateral arm flexion (180°)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is asked to raise and lower the extended right arm (palm in) as far as possible while keeping the head in a neutral position. The patient is then asked to raise and lower the extended left arm in the same way.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to keep the cervical spine stable during the arm movement • Compensatory movement of the cervical spine in rotation, lateral flexion, flexion or extension • Forward movement of the chin • Elevation or protraction of the shoulders
Bilateral arm flexion (180°)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is asked to raise and lower both arms (palms in) as far as possible while keeping the head still.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compensatory/excessive forward head movement or extension of the cervical spine observed during 180° of bilateral arm flexion
Bilateral arm flexion with weights (90°)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>The patient is instructed to lift two dumbbells (1 kg each for women and 2 kg each for men) with straight arms to chest height (90° shoulder flexion) and then to return with straight arms back.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protraction of the head • Forward movement of the chin • Extension of the cervical spine • Elevation of the shoulders
Upper cervical extension (in four-point kneeling)	Instruction	Criteria for inaccurate measurement
	<p>In four-point kneeling, the physiotherapist gently stabilises the C2 vertebra to help locate the movement in the upper cervical spine. The patient is instructed to imagine the axis of movement passing through the ear and to perform small craniocervical flexion and extension while maintaining the lower cervical spine in neutral position.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient is unable to dissociate upper cervical flexion-extension from lower cervical movement • Excessive lower cervical movement occurs • Inability to perform smooth and coordinated movements

During the measurement sequences, participants will receive standardised instructions for each of the 10 movement control measures. Participants will have the possibility to practise the required movement and familiarise themselves with the measure. The physiotherapist may provide verbal and tactile feedback during this practice phase. When the participant feels able to perform the measure correctly, the measure will be assessed. The physiotherapist will rate the measure as correct or not correct (criteria are given in table 3) and will not give any feedback. If the performance of the movement control measure is incorrect, the physiotherapist will have to indicate, why he/she judged the performance of the measurement to be incorrect (Aasa et al., 2014). The order of the 10 movement control measures will be randomized for each participant. The results of all measurements will be reported for each participant using a standardised form. After the measurement sequence, the project leader will accompany the participants to a separate room to fill out the Neck Disability Index (NDI) questionnaire (Swanenburg et al., 2014) and to answer a question on the pain intensity over the week prior to the measurement session. Participants without neck pain will do one measurement sequence. Participants with chronic neck pain will repeat the whole measurement sequence after a 30-minutes break with the other physiotherapist. Before starting the second measurement sequence, the participants will be asked again to report their current neck pain on the NRS, as before the first measurement sequence.

Reliability

To reflect normal clinical practice, we will investigate the whole measurement procedure, including instruction, execution and rating of the outcome of the measurement (De Vet et al., 2011). The data of the participants with chronic neck pain will be used for both the reliability and the validity part of the study.

Validity

To investigate discriminative validity and construct validity of the selected index measures in comparison with the hypothesized measures out of the 10 movement control measures, a known-group design will be used including participants with chronic neck pain and a sample of participants without neck pain (De Vet et al., 2011). Participants without neck pain will undergo one measurement sequence with one physiotherapist (random allocation to either physiotherapist 1 or physiotherapist 2) and their data will be used for the validity part of the study only. For the individual participant, the complete measurement session will take a maximum of 90 minutes for the participants with chronic neck pain (two measurement sequences of approximately 30 minutes each and a 30-minute break between the measurement sequences) and approximately 40 minutes for the participants without neck pain (one measurement sequence of approximately 30 minutes and approximately 10 minutes to complete the questionnaires). Table 4 gives an overview of the total project duration and table 5 shows the timing of the different assessments for each participant.

Table 4: Summary table project duration

Ethica approval			Recruitment physiotherapists									Data analysis		Writing manus cript	Submis sion
			Recruitment participants												
			Measurement sessions												
			↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓					
May 2025	Jun	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan 2026	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	July	

Table 5: Schedule of study procedure and assessments

Study step/Assessment	Before the measurement session	During the measurement session	
Oral and written information, participants have the possibility to ask questions	+		
Written informed consent	+		
Check inclusion / exclusion criteria	+		
		Participants with chronic neck pain and participants without neck pain	Only for participants with chronic neck pain
Standardised question: "Do you have neck pain for more than 3 months? By neck pain for more than 3 months, we mean that you have constant or recurring episodes of neck pain for more than 3 months." (Answer: Yes/No).		+	
Question about current neck pain intensity (NRS)		+	
Random allocation to physiotherapist 1 or physiotherapist 2		+	
Assessment of the 10 movement control measures		+	
Neck Disability Index		+	
Pain intensity over last week		+	
30-minutes break			+
Question about current neck pain intensity (NRS)			+
Assessment of the 10 movement control measures by the other physiotherapist			+

3.4 Withdrawal and discontinuation

As participants are invited to attend only one measurement session, we do not expect any dropouts during the study. However, if a participant does not complete the measurement session, the (incomplete) data will be analyzed. If a participant withdraws consent, the participant's data will be deleted.

If a physiotherapist withdraws from the study before the end of the agreed measurement dates, the data collected up to that point will be analysed.

4 STATISTICS AND METHODOLOGY

4.1. Statistical analysis plan

The study population will be described, and characteristics will be presented in a table. Following the recommendations from the COSMIN group, we aim to have 50 complete data sets for each measure from participants with chronic neck pain and 50 complete data sets for each measure from participants without neck pain (De Vet et al., 2011).

To determine inter-rater reliability, both measurement sequences of the participants with chronic neck pain will be analysed, because reliability has to be measured in a population that is comparable to the population where the measures will be applied in clinical practice (De Vet et al., 2011). We will calculate unweighted Cohen's kappa (kappa value and 95% CI). As we will collect nominal data, it is not possible to calculate a parameter of measurement error expressed in units of measurement. We will calculate the percentage of agreement between the ratings of the different raters for the 10 measures. We will use the classification of Landis and Koch (1977) to interpret the results, and additionally, to allow for better interpretation of the results, the content of the cross-tables will be presented (De Vet et al., 2011).

For discriminative validity and for construct validity, the first measurement sequence of all participants (participants with chronic neck pain and participants without neck pain) will be used for analysis. For discriminative validity, we will collect dichotomous data (the measurement outcomes will be rated as correct or incorrect) and the data will be analysed compared to the chosen gold standard, which in our case will be the answer to the standardised question if the participant has chronic neck pain or not. Results will be presented in a 2x2 table with four possibilities of results: the movement control measure can be rated as either positive or negative and the participant can suffer from chronic neck pain or not. In the 2x2 table, two of the four possible results are correct (true positive and true negative result), and two results not (false positive and false negative result) (Fletcher, 2019). We estimate that with a sample of 50 complete data sets from each group (participants with chronic neck pain and participants without neck pain), we will collect enough data to have results in all four cells (De Vet et al., 2011). We will calculate sensitivity, specificity and predictive values and report the results in relation to the a priori defined criterion for accepting discriminative validity of the measures. Regarding construct validity, correlations between the index measures and their chosen comparators are calculated and interpreted according to the hypotheses. For each hypothesis, it will be shown whether the hypothesis has been confirmed or whether it has been refuted.

Our analyses will not be gender specific. The aim of the study is to investigate aspects of reliability and validity of measures in a population reflecting normal clinical practice, and the issues of sex and gender are not relevant in this case.

4.2. Handling of missing data

If we have missing data, in the sense that a participant's data are incomplete because he or she was unable to complete the measurement session, but did not withdraw from the study, the incomplete data will be analysed. We aim to collect 50 complete data sets from participants with chronic neck pain and 50 complete data sets from participants without neck pain. Based on a potential drop-out rate of 10%, we plan to recruit 56 participants in each group.

5 REGULATORY ASPECTS AND SAFETY

5.1 Local regulations / Declaration of Helsinki

This research project will be conducted in accordance with the protocol, the Declaration of Helsinki and the principles of Good Clinical Practice. The project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Vaud, Switzerland.

6 FUNDING / PUBLICATION / DECLARATION OF INTEREST

This project is mainly funded by the HES-SO School of Health. We will publish the results of this project independently in an open access peer-reviewed journal. The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

7 REFERENCES

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